

Week	California					Texas					Mississippi					Florida														
	Betray	Auth	Sanct	Subv	Degrad	Betray	Auth	Sanct	Subv	Degrad	UP	DOWN	Care	Harm	Fair	Cheat	Loyal	Betray	Auth	Sanct	Subv	Degrad								
Week 1	Jan 19-25																													
Week 2	Jan 26-Feb 1																													
Week 3	Feb 2-Feb 8																													
Week 4	Feb 9-Feb 15																													
Week 5	Feb 16-Feb 22																													
Week 6	Feb 23-Feb 29																													
Week 7	Mar 1-Mar 7			1	1			1	1				2		1		1		1											
Week 8	Mar 8-Mar 14		2		4		1		4						1		1		1											
Week 9	Mar 15-Mar 21		1	1	5				1				2		6		2			1										
Week 10	Mar 22-Mar 28		1		4		2		1				1		2					2										
Week 11	Mar 29-Apr 4		2		4				2						5		1		2	1										
Week 12	Apr 5-Apr 11		1		2				1						3				1	1										
Week 13	Apr 12-Apr 18				1		2						1		6		2		2	3										
Week 14	Apr 19-Apr 25		1				1								1															
Week 15	Apr 26-May 2			1	1		1																							
Week 16	May 3-May 9								1																					
Week 17	May 10-May 16				1		1		2										1	1										
Week 18	May 17-May 23		1	1	1		1		1						2															
Week 19	May 24-May 30						1								1															
Week 20	May 31-Jun 6				1		1		3													1								
Week 21	Jun 7-Jun 13				1		1																							
Week 22	Jun 14-Jun 20		1		1																									
Week 23	Jun 21-Jun 27			1																										
Week 24	Jun 28-Jul 4						1		1				1		1				1											
Week 25	Jul 5-Jul 11		1		1								1																	
Week 26	Jul 12-Jul 18								1																					
Week 27	Jul 19-Jul 25												1						1											
Week 28	Jul 26-Aug 1				1				2				1																	
Week 29	Aug 2-Aug 8								1				1								1									
Week 30	Aug 9-Aug 15		1						1											1										
Week 31	Aug 16-Aug 22								1						1						1									
Week 32	Aug 23-Aug 29								1						1															
Week 33	Aug 30-Sep 5				1								1		1		1				1									
Week 34	Sep 6-Sep 12																													
Week 35	Sep 13-Sep 19												1																	
Week 36	Sep 20-Sep 26																													
Week 37	Sep 27-Oct 3				1										1															
Week 38	Oct 4-Oct 10																													
Week 39	Oct 11-Oct 17				1				1												1									
Week 40	Oct 18-Oct 24														2															
Week 41	Oct 25-Oct 31																													
Week 42	Nov 1-Nov 7		1		1				2																					
			13	5	33	0	11	0	5	28	0	0	87	152					14	0	33	0	8	0	11	13	0	1	64	108

<https://www.mass.gov/orgs/department-of-public-health/news>
<https://www.dshs.texas.gov/news/releases.shtm>
<https://www.health.ny.gov/press/releases/>
<https://www.countyofglenn.net/dept/health-human-services/public-health/covid-19/california-department-public-health>
<http://www.floridahealth.gov/newsroom/>
<https://www.dshs.texas.gov/news/releases.shtm>
<https://www.mass.gov/orgs/department-of-public-health/news>
<https://msdh.ms.gov/msdhsite/index.cfm/23,0,341.html>
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